

POLITICAL SCIENCES

ISLAM AND GENDER: UNDERSTANDING THE COMPLEXITIES

Laliashvili M.

PhD Student,

Georgian Technical University

Abstract

In Islam, like in many big religions, gender has a complex role. Research of this topic reveals a rich history of diverse interpretations and practices of relationship between gender and religion. This article explores the historical developments and contemporary complexities related to the gender in Islam. Despite the perception of Islam having strict and traditional gender roles, the modern reality is much more different and diverse. It highlights the ways in which gender intersects with other aspects of identity, especially in Muslim-dominated societies in the world.

This article digs into the foundational Islamic texts *the Quran*, which emphasize both spiritual equality and differentiated social roles for men and women. The rise of Islamic feminism is challenging these traditional rules and traditions, advocating for a reinterpretation of Islamic teachings and adapting to the modern principles of gender equality. Contemporary world requires a deeper understanding of the evolving discourse on Islam and gender, providing insights into opportunities for reform.

Keywords: Gender, Islamic feminism, Patriarchy, Muslim, society, human rights, culture.

Introduction:

Islam is often described in popular discourse as a monolithic religion with strict gender roles and Islamic norms. However, the reality is more deep and complex. In fact, the relationship between Islam and gender is shaped by a variety of factors, such as history, culture, traditions and other social and political aspects of a particular society, especially Muslim-dominated. The various interpretations and practices of Islam across the world and across different Muslim communities is also an important issue to consider. Some practices of Islam emphasize strict gender roles, while others give emphasize to relatively unrestricted approaches. It is noteworthy that the *Quran* and the teachings of Prophet Muhammad articulate principles of both spiritual equality and differentiated social functions for men and women. They provide a framework for a balanced and just society, where both genders can contribute meaningfully and equally to the community. In the modern era, the rise of Islamic feminism, alongside global movements advocating for gender equality, has challenged traditional readings of Islamic law, prompting discussions on women's rights, leadership roles, and the interpretation of family law.

Historically, from early days of Islam, women played significant roles in various aspects of community life in society and were actively engaged in economic, social and other spheres in Islamic societies. In pre-Islamic era the role of women varies in different societies. For instance, in Pre-Islamic Arabia women had limited rights and were often marginalized, while in Pre-Islamic Yemen women held positions of power (such as the legendary queen Shamsi). The Quran granting women rights, including the rights of inheriting property and right to decide matters related to their marriage, divorce and other personal freedoms. In early Islamic societies women started to participate in various aspects of community life, such as trade, agricul-

ture, and education. For example, the Prophet Muhammad's wife – Aisha was a respected scholar who transmitted many hadiths (reports of the Prophet's sayings and actions) and contributing to the intellectual and spiritual life of the Muslim community at that time. Another wife Khadijah, was a significant supporter of his prophetic mission.

While looking deepen in the Quran several verses are emphasizing the foundation for gender equality. Specifically, the Quran:

- states that men and women were created from a single soul (Quran 4:1). Men and women are considered equal in their humanity and are equally responsible for fulfilling their religious duties and obligations.
- states that men and women will be rewarded or punished based on their actions and does not make any distinction based on gender (Quran 3:195, 33:35).
- grants women various legal rights, including the right to inheritance (Quran 4:7-11), the right to choose their spouses (Quran 2:221), and the right to seek divorce under certain circumstances (Quran 2:228-229).
- encourages men and women to seek knowledge (Quran 20:114) and spiritual growth.
- emphasizes the importance of men and women adhering to high standards of moral conduct and ethical behavior (Quran 33:35, 49:13). Both genders are equally accountable to their duties within families and communities, they live in.

The gender roles within Muslim societies have been also shaped by historical developments and certain political and cultural circumstances. While the Quran called for justice and mutual respect in marriage, it also assigned different responsibilities to men and women. Men are described as protectors and providers laying ground for obvious patriarchal interpretations of the men's role in the societies. In the medieval Islamic period the role of women became increasingly shaped

by the social and cultural conditions of particular Islamic communities in certain regions into which Islam spread. This era was also important in terms of *Sharia* - Islamic law, which gradually transformed into a more formalized legal system and started interpretation of the Quran in a certain way. The Islamic law maintained some of the rights granted to women by the Quran, while concerning some aspects such as marriage and divorce, and inheritance men started to have greater legal authorities. Female participation in public life also started to diminish. Despite these new realities, women maintained capacity to participate in cultural life. Their main focus shifted to education and the spread of knowledge.

Gender roles further altered in the Post-Colonial periods, which was characterized by significant changes in political, social, economic, and political structures. The rise of nationalist movements in this period contributed to the redefinition of gender roles in many Muslim-majority societies. In Turkey, Tunisia, and Egypt, major reforms have been implemented to improve women's rights in areas such as education, culture, employment, and family law. In parallel some Islamist movements that emerged in response to this secularization process started advocating for more restricted roles for women and provided patriarchal interpretations of Islamic texts.

Nevertheless, the world is changing and new global dynamics is dictating different realities. Today Islamic feminism has become a growing movement within Muslim societies, which argue that many of the interpretations of the gender role in Muslim communities are not inherent in Islam and these gender inequalities need to be addressed. Tunisia, Morocco, and Malaysia have made significant strides in legal reforms that improve women's rights. In modern world, social media has been playing a very important role in terms of reaching out more women, empowering them to advocate for their rights, equality. New realities are also requesting women's greater participation in politics, education, culture and other spheres in Islamic communities.

Despite the Islamic feminists' movement, some societies and conservative religious authorities resist such efforts and continue to advocate for conservative interpretations of Islam, which remains one of the main obstacles to achieving gender equality. In these societies conservative norms and traditions deeply rooted and women are expected to follow these norms prioritizing family responsibilities over public life and fulfillments of their rights. The limitation of women's rights can be rooted in very details of everyday life. Examples of means of controlling women and limiting their visibility in public spaces are the practices of *purdah*, in other words seclusion of women and *hijab*. *Some women, of course*, choose to wear hijab as a personal choice as an expression of their faith, but in some societies, it is strictly legally mandated to wear them despite women's will and choice. In some Islamic societies, such as Afghanistan, restrictions are imposed on women's mobility, marriage, their right for employ-

ment, education, employment, political and social participation. In many Muslim countries, religious institutions are male-dominated, and women are often excluded from positions of leadership and religious authority. This lack of female representation in religious decision-making bodies perpetuates interpretations of Islamic law that marginalize women and fail to address their concerns adequately. Legal disparities are also an issue. New generations of women who are born and raised in these societies are not only deprived of the basic rights, but also are limited to challenge gender inequalities and advocate for their rights.

In many Islamic traditions, men have the unilateral right to divorce their wives. This tradition is called *talaq*. Meanwhile women face more strict rules to initiate divorce. Also child custody laws often favor fathers. This creates an imbalance in marital power dynamics and often leaves women vulnerable to social and economic insecurity after divorce, having limited or no access to alimony or property rights. Although these traditions being deeply rooted, there are examples of Tunisia⁸, Morocco and other countries, which have successfully reformed the family laws and made substantial steps forward toward achieving gender equality in their countries. In contrast, in other countries like Saudi Arabia or Iran, legal reforms have been minimal or have reinforced patriarchal norms, limiting women's autonomy and access to justice.

Nevertheless, addressing gender issues is not only a question of religious reform, but also of challenging long-standing cultural traditions. Efforts to reform gender relations are frequently met with resistance because they are perceived as threats to the cultural and social identity. The cultural resistance is especially strong in rural and conservative areas, where local customs may hold more influence than religious texts. Any attempts to promote gender equality are often portrayed as Western impositions that seek to undermine Muslim identity and values, creating a significant challenge for advocates of gender reform. Some Islamic groups portray gender equality as part of a broader Western agenda to undermine Islamic values and traditions, and further promote anti-Western movements.

There are also differences between Sunni and Shia interpretations of Islamic law. Between them, Sunni Islam generally adheres to a stricter interpretation of gender roles. Shia Islam also acknowledges the unique spiritual authority of the Imams, who are believed to have divine insight and authority that include spiritual guidance over men and women. In Sunni Islam, there has traditionally been less emphasis on such spiritual figures, and authority is more widely dispersed across religious scholars. Sunni interpretations generally maintain a more conservative approach to gender roles, often emphasizing a model of distinct, complementary roles for men and women based on hadith and legal precedent. Both Sunni and Shia Islamic laws allocate specific rights and responsibilities to men and women within the family. In terms of inheritance, both traditions generally follow the Quran which allocate a larger share of inheritance to male heirs, justified by the responsibility of men to provide financial support to the

⁸ Tunisia's 1956 Personal Status Code

family. However, interpretations vary too. Shia law, for example, may allow for slightly more tolerant interpretations in certain cases, while Sunni law remains more strict.

Marriage roles also differ - Sunni jurisprudence places a strong emphasis on obedience to the husband within the marriage relationship, while Shia law incorporates a more nuanced perspective by allowing for greater negotiation in marital contracts. For example, in Shia law, a woman may include specific stipulations within her marriage contract that can protect her rights within the marriage, such as the right to work or the right to certain financial autonomy. This provision allows for a greater degree of autonomy for Shia women in their marital relationships compared to stricter Sunni rules.

Opportunities for progress and change - The discourse surrounding gender roles in Islam is gradually evolving and calling for re-examination of traditional interpretations of Islamic norms to reflect contemporary realities and promote gender equality. While challenges persist, there are numerous opportunities for progress and change regarding gender within Muslim communities. These opportunities stem from the re-engagement with Islamic texts through reformist interpretations, the emergence of Islamic feminism, legal reforms in Muslim-majority countries, and the influence of global human rights movements. By returning to the egalitarian principles present in the Quran, reformist thinkers are able to advocate for gender equality while remaining faithful to Islamic tradition. Re-reading of the Quran from a gender-inclusive perspective is key, emphasizing on justice, equality, and human dignity for all believers, regardless they are men or women.

One key area of reformist interpretation focuses on the concept of *ijtihad*, or independent reasoning. *Ijtihad* allows for flexibility in interpreting Islamic law in response to changing social conditions. While it has been historically restricted, many contemporary Muslim scholars advocate for its revival to address modern issues such as gender inequality. By applying *ijtihad*, scholars can offer new readings of texts that emphasize justice, equality, and compassion—core values in Islam.

For example, traditional interpretations of *Surah Al-Nisa*, which describes men as the "protectors and maintainers" of women, have been used to justify male authority. However, reformist scholars like Amina Wadud have re-interpreted this verse, emphasizing that protection and maintenance are not about domination but rather about responsibility and mutual support between genders. This shift in interpretation can foster a more balanced understanding of gender roles, rooted in partnership rather than hierarchy.

Re-thinking and re-evaluating *sharia* law can also create opportunities for addressing specific legal inequalities, such as those related to divorce, inheritance, and child custody. Reformist scholars advocate for applying Islamic principles of fairness and justice to ensure that women are not disadvantaged by traditional legal structures.

Islamic feminism represents another critical opportunity for advancing gender equality within the

framework of Islamic values. Unlike secular feminism, which is often viewed with skepticism in Muslim-dominated societies, as it is perceived as a separate movement from religion, Islamic feminism resonates more within Islamic groups. In general, Islamic feminists challenge practices such as polygamy, unequal inheritance rights, and male-centered interpretations of family law. They argue that these practices are not fundamental to Islam but rather the product of interpretations of various patriarchal movements. By reclaiming Islamic texts and traditions, Islamic feminists offer an opportunity for gender justice that is both authentically Islamic and aligned with modern principles of equality. Moreover, Islamic feminists have successfully mobilized in various countries to influence legal reforms and raise awareness about women's rights. The activism of women's organizations in countries like Morocco, Tunisia, and Malaysia has resulted in tangible changes to family law, including reforms to divorce procedures, inheritance rights, and the abolition of polygamy.

An interesting example of legal reform is Personal Status Code adopted in Tunisia in 1956, which was one of the most progressive family laws in the Muslim world at the time. The Personal Status Code abolished polygamy, established legal equality between men and women (in marriage and divorce), and granted women the right to custody of their children. Tunisia has continued to lead the way in promoting gender equality, with the recent 2017 law allowing Muslim women to marry non-Muslim men. Another important case is Morocco's 2004 Moudawana (family code), which granted women more equal rights in marriage and divorce, as well as child custody. Moudawana raised the minimum age of marriage for girls to 18. All these reforms were framed within an Islamic context, having no relation to any kind of Western influence, demonstrating that gender equality can be pursued with respect to Islamic values.

Promoting women's political participation is another area to emphasize. Having female heads of states, ministers, governors, etc is another big step toward gender equality in muslim-majority countries. Turkey, Indonesia, Pakistan and Bangladesh have showed a very good examples of women's political activity and participation.

The role of education is key. In many Muslim-majority countries, women's access to education has significantly improved, and women are increasingly participating in higher education and professional fields. This shift has profound implications for gender relations, as educated women are more likely to challenge traditional gender roles and advocate for their rights within their communities. Furthermore, the rise of female scholars in Islamic studies is contributing to a more inclusive discourse on gender within Islam.

With the rise of social media, social activism along with digital activism can play a very important role in promoting awareness on gender equality, advocating for legal and social reforms, facilitating connection between various activists and likeminded groups. Collaborating with religious leaders, government and international organizations could be of an added value too.

Conclusion

Addressing gender issues within the Muslim community is a complex and multifaceted challenge, involving religious, cultural, legal, and socio-political dynamics. Religious interpretations that uphold patriarchal norms, strict rules disadvantaging women, all contribute to the difficulties in promoting gender equality in Muslim societies.

Despite these challenges, there are also opportunities for progress. Reformist movements within Islam, such as Islamic feminism, are gaining traction, calling for a re-examination of the Quran and *Islamic* principles to reflect contemporary realities and come in line with gender equality in Islamic societies. Examples of successful legal reforms in some Muslim-majority countries, like Turkey, Tunisia and others demonstrate the possibility and potential for aligning Islamic principles with gender justice.

Undoubtedly, addressing gender issues in the Muslim community requires a delicate approach, respecting religious deep-rooted traditions while advocating for the women rights and their dignity. By engaging in a lively debate within Muslim communities regarding gender roles and women's rights, having thoughtful and respectful dialogue despite diverse opinions, addressing challenges and creating more equitable and just societies for all shall be possible. The solid foundation for this is the early role of women in Islamic societies which far more dynamic and multifaceted than is often assumed. Islam brought significant improvements to the status of women, granting them rights and opportunities that were unprecedented in pre-Islamic Arabian society. By understanding and appreciating the historical perspectives on women in early Islamic societies, we can gain a more nuanced understanding of the role of women in Islam and challenge misconceptions about gender in Islamic history.

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